

Neutrosophic Fuzzy Bi-Ideal of BS-Algebras

P. Ayesha Parveen¹, M. Himaya Jaleela Begum²

^{1,2}Department of Mathematics, Sadakathullah Appa College, Tirunelveli-11, Tamil Nadu, India.

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 17 February 2023 Corresponding Author: P. Ayesha Parveen	The main aim of this paper is to introduce the new concept of neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras. Some algebraic nature are investigated. Neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras is also applied in Cartesian product. Finally, we also provide the homomorphic behaviour of neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras.
KEYWORDS: BS-algebras, Neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal, Cartesian product, Homomorphism.	

1. INTRODUCTION

After the introduction of fuzzy subsets by L.A.Zadeh[7], several researches explored on the generalization of the notion of fuzzy subset. In 1966, Imai and Iseki introduced two classes of abstract algebras viz. BCK-algebras and BCI-algebras[2]. J.Neggers and H.S. Kim introduced the notion of B-algebras[3] which is a generalisation of BCK-algebras. We introduce the notion of BS-algebras which is a generalisation of B-algebras and established the notion of Doubt fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras[1]. F. Smarandache[4] extended the concept of fuzzy logic to neutrosophic logic which includes indeterminacy. Neutrosophic set theory played a major role in decision making problem, medical diagnosis, robotics, image processing, etc.,

In this paper, we introduced the notion of Neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras and studied their algebraic properties. We obtained the Cartesian product of neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal for BS-algebras. Finally, we studied how to deal with homomorphism in neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal for BS-algebras.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this Section, We recall some basic definitions which are needed for our study.

Definition 2.1 [1]. A BS-Algebra \mathfrak{B} is a non empty set with a constant 1 and a binary operation $*$ satisfying the following axioms

- (i) $a*a=1$
- (ii) $a*1=a$
- (iii) $(a*b)*c = a*(c*(1*b)) \forall a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}$

Definition 2.2 [1]. A fuzzy subset F in a BS-Algebra \mathfrak{B} is called Fuzzy Bi-Ideal if

- (i) $F(1) \geq F(a)$
- (ii) $F(b*c) \geq \min\{F(a), F(a*(b*c))\} \forall a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}$

Example 2.3 [1]. Let $\mathfrak{B} = \{1, x, y, z\}$ be a set with the following Cayley table

*	1	x	y	z
1	1	x	y	z
x	x	1	z	y
y	y	z	1	x
z	z	y	x	1

Then $(\mathfrak{B}, *, 1)$ is a BS-algebra. Define a fuzzy set $F: \mathfrak{B} \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $F(1)=F(b)=0.9$ and $F(a)=F(c)=0.7$. Then F is a fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} .

Definition 2.4 [5]. A Neutrosophic fuzzy set \mathcal{N} on the Universe of discourse X characterised by a truth membership function $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)$, an indeterminacy function $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)$ and a falsity membership function $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)$ is defined as $\mathcal{N} = \{ \langle a, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a) \rangle : a \in X \}$ where $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}} : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $0 \leq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}} + \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}} + \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}} \leq 3$

Definition 2.5 [5]. Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} . Then $a \in \mathfrak{B}$

- i) $\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N} = \{ \langle a, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) \rangle \}$, where $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) = \max(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)); \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) = \min(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) = \min(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))$

ii) $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N} = \{ \langle a, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) \rangle$, where
 $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) = \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}$; $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) = \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}$; $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) = \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}$

3. NEUTROSOPHIC FUZZY BI IDEAL OF BS-ALGEBRAS

In this section, we give the definition for Neutrosophic Fuzzy Bi-Ideal of BS-Algebras and studied some of their algebraic properties.

Definition 3.1. A Neutrosophic fuzzy set \mathcal{N} of BS-Algebras \mathfrak{B} is called a Neutrosophic Fuzzy Bi-Ideal of \mathfrak{B} if $\forall a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}$

$$(\mathcal{N}_1) \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a); \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a); \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a);$$

$$(\mathcal{N}_2) \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\};$$

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\};$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

Theorem 3.2. Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} . Then $\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi ideal of \mathfrak{B} .

Proof

Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} . For any $a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(1) &= \max\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\geq \max\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\} \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(1) &\geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) \\ \text{And } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(1) &= \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\} \\ &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(1) &= \min\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \min\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) &= \max\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(b^*c), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)\} \\ &\geq \max\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c))\}, \\ &\quad \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \min\{\max\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) &= \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(b^*c), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)\} \\ &\leq \min\{\max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c))\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}, \min\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c)), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) &= \min\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(b^*c), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)\} \\ &\leq \min\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c))\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\min\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}, \\ &\quad \min\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c)), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

Hence, $\mathcal{M} \cup \mathcal{N}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}

Theorem 3.3. Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} . Then $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi ideal of \mathfrak{B} .

Proof

Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B} . For any $a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(1) &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\} \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Therefore, } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(1) &\geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) \\ \text{And } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(1) &= \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\} \\ &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(1) &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) &= \max\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(b^*c), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c))\}, \\ &\quad \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}, \\ &\quad \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) &= \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(b^*c), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c))\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c)), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(b^*c), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c))\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)\}, \\ &\quad \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a^*(b^*c)), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(b^*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}}(a^*(b^*c))\}$$

Hence, $\mathcal{M} \cap \mathcal{N}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}

Corollary 3.4. Let $\mathcal{M}_1, \mathcal{M}_2, \dots, \mathcal{M}_n$ are neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} , then $\mathcal{M} = \bigcap_{i=1}^n \mathcal{M}_i$ is also a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}

Lemma 3.5. For all $s, t \in I$ and i be any positive integer, if $s = t$, then

- i) $s^i \leq t^i$
- ii) $[\min(s, t)]^i = \min(s^i, t^i)$
- iii) $[\max(s, t)]^i = \max(s^i, t^i)$

Theorem 3.6. Let \mathcal{N} be a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} , then $\mathcal{N}^i = \{ \langle a, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) \rangle : a \in \mathfrak{B} \}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}^i , where i is any positive integer and $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) = (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) = (\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) = (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i$

Proof

Let \mathcal{N} be a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B} . For any $a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(1) &= (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1))^i \\ &\geq (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(1) &= (\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(1))^i \\ &\leq (\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i \\ &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(1) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(1) &= (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1))^i \\ &\leq (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(b*c) &= (\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b*c))^i \\ &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a*(b*c))\}^i \\ &= \min\{(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i, \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a*(b*c))^i\} \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a*(b*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(b*c) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a*(b*c))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(b*c) &= (\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(b*c))^i \\ &\leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a*(b*c))\}^i \\ &= \max\{(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i, \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a*(b*c))^i\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a*(b*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(b*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a*(b*c))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(b*c) &= (\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b*c))^i \\ &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a*(b*c))\}^i \\ &= \max\{(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))^i, \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a*(b*c))^i\} \\ &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a*(b*c))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(b*c) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}^i}(a*(b*c))\}$

Hence \mathcal{N}^i be a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}^i

4. DIRECT PRODUCT OF NEUTROSOPHIC FUZZY BI IDEAL OF BS-ALGEBRAS

In this Section, we shall discuss with the direct product of neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideals of BS-Algebras.

Definition 4.1. Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy subsets of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively. Then the direct product of neutrosophic fuzzy subsets of BS-algebras \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 is defined by $\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N} : \mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2 \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N} = \{ \langle (a, b), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a, b), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a, b), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a, b) \rangle : a \in \mathfrak{B}_1, b \in \mathfrak{B}_2 \}$, where $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a, b) = \min(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b));$

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a, b) = \max(\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(b));$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a, b) = \min(\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b))$$

Definition 4.2. Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy subsets of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively. Then $\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of $\mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$ if it satisfies the following conditions

$$\text{i) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2); \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) \leq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2);$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) \leq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2);$$

$$\text{ii) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) \geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)))\};$$

$$\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) \leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)))\};$$

$$\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) \leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)))\}$$

Theorem 4.3. Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideals of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively. Then $\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideals of $\mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$

Proof

Let \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{N} be two neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideals of BS-algebra \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 respectively.

Let $(a_1, a_2), (b_1, b_2), (c_1, c_2) \in \mathfrak{B}_1 \times \mathfrak{B}_2$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i) } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2)\} \\ &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) \geq \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again } \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) &= \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2)\} \\ &= \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) \geq \mathcal{I}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again } \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) &= \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(1), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2)\} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(1, 1) \geq \mathcal{F}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ii) Then } \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) &= \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(b_1*c_1, b_2*c_2) \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(b_1*c_1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2*c_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \min[\min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1*(b_1*c_1))\}, \\ &\quad \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2*(b_2*c_2))\}] \\ &= \min[\min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2)\}, \\ &\quad \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1*(b_1*c_1)), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2*(b_2*c_2))\}] \\ &= \min\{\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{N}}(a_1*(b_1*c_1), (a_2*(b_2*c_2))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*(b, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2))\} \\
 \text{Therefore, } &\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) \geq \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \\
 &\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*(b, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2))\} \\
 \text{And } &\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}}(b_1^*c_1, b_2^*c_2) \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}}(b_1^*c_1), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2^*c_2)\} \\
 &\leq \max[\max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1^*(b_1^*c_1))\}, \\
 &\quad \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2^*(b_2^*c_2))\}] \\
 &= \max[\max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2)\}, \\
 &\quad \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1^*(b_1^*c_1)), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2^*(b_2^*c_2))\}] \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1^*(b_1^*c_1), a_2^*(b_2^*c_2))\} \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*(b, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2))\} \\
 \text{Therefore, } &\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) \leq \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \\
 &\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*(b, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2))\} \\
 \text{And } &\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) = \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(b_1^*c_1, b_2^*c_2) \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(b_1^*c_1), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2^*c_2)\} \\
 &\leq \max[\max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1^*(b_1^*c_1))\}, \\
 &\quad \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2^*(b_2^*c_2))\}] \\
 &= \max[\max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2)\}, \\
 &\quad \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}}(a_1^*(b_1^*c_1)), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2^*(b_2^*c_2))\}] \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1^*(b_1^*c_1), a_2^*(b_2^*c_2))\} \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*(b, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2))\} \\
 \text{Therefore, } &\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((b_1, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2)) \leq \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}(a_1, a_2), \\
 &\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{M}\times\mathcal{N}}((a_1, a_2)^*(b, b_2)^*(c_1, c_2))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

5. HOMOMORPHISM OF NEUTROSOPHIC FUZZY BI IDEAL OF BS-ALGEBRAS

In this section, we discuss about homomorphism

Definition 5.1. Let \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 be two BS-algebras and $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be a function. If \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic fuzzy set in \mathfrak{B}_2 , then the preimage of \mathcal{N} under h denoted by $h^{-1}(\mathcal{N})$ is the neutrosophic fuzzy set in \mathfrak{B}_1 is defined by $h^{-1}(\mathcal{N}) = \{ \langle a, h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)), h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)), h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) \rangle : a \in \mathfrak{B}_2 \}$, where $h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) = \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a))$; $h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a))$; $h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) = \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a))$

Theorem 5.2. Let $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be an epimorphism of BS-algebras if \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}_2 , then the pre image of \mathcal{N} under h is also a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}_1 .

Proof

Let \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}_2 . Let $a, b, c \in \mathfrak{B}_1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Now, } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) = \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(1)) \\
 &\geq \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) \\
 \text{Therefore } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) \geq h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) \\
 \text{And } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(1)) \\
 &\leq \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) \\
 \text{Therefore } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) \leq h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{And } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) = \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(1)) \\
 &\leq \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) \\
 \text{Therefore } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) \leq h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a)) \\
 \text{And, } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)) = \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(b^*c)) \\
 &= \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(b)^*h(c)) \\
 &\geq \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)^*[h(b)^*h(c)])\} \\
 &= \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a^*(b^*c)))\} \\
 \text{Therefore, } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)) \geq \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a^*(b^*c)))\} \\
 \text{And } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)) = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(b^*c)) \\
 &= \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(b)^*h(c)) \\
 &\leq \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)^*[h(b)^*h(c)])\} \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a^*(b^*c)))\} \\
 \text{Therefore, } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)) \leq \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a^*(b^*c)))\} \\
 \text{And } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)) = \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(b^*c)) \\
 &= \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(b)^*h(c)) \\
 &\leq \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)^*[h(b)^*h(c)])\} \\
 &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a^*(b^*c)))\} \\
 \text{Therefore, } &h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b^*c)) \leq \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a)), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a^*(b^*c)))\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 5.3. Let \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 be two BS-algebras and $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be a homomorphism. Then $h(1) = 1$

Proof

Let \mathfrak{B}_1 and \mathfrak{B}_2 be two BS-algebras

Let $a \in \mathfrak{B}_1$ therefore $h(a) \in \mathfrak{B}_2$

Now $h(1) = h(a^*a) = h(a)^*h(a) = 1^*1 = 1$

Theorem 5.4. Let $h: \mathfrak{B}_1 \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}_2$ be a homomorphism of BS-algebras if \mathcal{N} is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}_1 , then $h(\mathcal{N})$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of \mathfrak{B}_2 .

Proof

Let $a_1, a_2, a_3 \in \mathfrak{B}_1$ and $b_1, b_2, b_3 \in \mathfrak{B}_2$ such that $h(a_1) = b_1$, $h(a_2) = b_2$, $h(a_3) = b_3$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Now, } &\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1) = \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1)) \\
 &\leq h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) \\
 &= \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(1)) \\
 &= \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1) \leq \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{And } &\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1) = \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)) \\
 &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1)) \\
 &\geq h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) \\
 &= \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(1)) \\
 &= \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1) \geq \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1) &= \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1)) \\ &\geq h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)) \\ &= \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(1)) \\ &= \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1) \geq \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(1)$

ii) Again we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2 * b_3) &= \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_2) * h(a_3)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2 * a_3)) \\ &\geq \min\{h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1)), h^{-1}(\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1 * (a_2 * a_3)))\} \\ &= \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1 * (a_2 * a_3)))\} \\ &= \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1) * (h(a_2) * h(a_3)))\} \\ &= \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1 * (b_2 * b_3))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2 * b_3) \geq \min\{\mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1), \mathbb{T}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1 * (b_2 * b_3))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2 * b_3) &= \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_2) * h(a_3)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2 * a_3)) \\ &\leq \max\{h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1)), h^{-1}(\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1 * (a_2 * a_3)))\} \\ &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1 * (a_2 * a_3)))\} \\ &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1) * (h(a_2) * h(a_3)))\} \\ &= \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1 * (b_2 * b_3))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2 * b_3) \leq \max\{\mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1), \mathbb{L}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1 * (b_2 * b_3))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{And } \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2 * b_3) &= \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_2) * h(a_3)) \\ &= h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_2 * a_3)) \\ &\leq \max\{h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1)), h^{-1}(\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(a_1 * (a_2 * a_3)))\} \\ &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1 * (a_2 * a_3)))\} \\ &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1)), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(h(a_1) * (h(a_2) * h(a_3)))\} \\ &= \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1 * (b_2 * b_3))\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_2 * b_3) \leq \max\{\mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1), \mathbb{F}_{\mathcal{N}}(b_1 * (b_2 * b_3))\}$

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the notion of Neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal of BS-algebras are introduced and studied their algebraic properties. We obtained the Cartesian product of neutrosophic fuzzy bi-ideal for BS-algebras. Finally, we studied how to deal with homomorphism.

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